

Earth system functioning as a separate area of protection for life cycle impact assessment

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Abstract

Areas of protection (AoPs) guide what is considered to be the goal of environmental protection in life cycle assessment (LCA). Currently, the general agreement is on including three AoPs of human health, ecosystem quality, and natural resources. These AoPs determine the considered impact pathways, the included impact categories, and the design of the models used to quantify the impacts. However, the current LCA framework does not directly reflect the knowledge of Earth system science and the critical role of Earth system functioning. This paper advocates for an additional Earth system AoP to extend the horizon of LCA studies with impacts on the Earth system functioning and stability. It is argued that the proposed Earth system AoP would satisfy selection criteria based on societal consensus, intrinsic value, functional value, as well as cultural value. Including the Earth system as an AoP would allow LCA to consider different impact pathways and thus different dimensions of the current environmental problems. The included impact pathways and the design of impact categories could be based on the knowledge from Earth system science and inspired by the planetary boundaries framework. This is but a first attempt at a broad conceptualization of an Earth system AoP which would require further scientific debate and methodological development to be fully operational.

KEYWORDS

areas of protection, earth system, impact pathway, life cycle assessment, life cycle impact assessment, planetary boundaries

1 | INTRODUCTION

The life cycle assessment (LCA) method was established with the purpose of quantifying “*damage to elements in the environment and on elements in the economy, which are affected through environmental processes*” (Udo de Haes & Lindeijer, 2002, p. 218). What is to be considered in a full environmental LCA is largely determined through the selection of the areas of protection (AoPs), also known as safeguard subjects. These AoPs outline what is considered as the ultimate goal of environmental protection. As the target of protection, the AoPs determine the impact pathways that should be considered; and the impact pathways, at least in theory, determine the included impact categories, the models used to calculate them, and ultimately the environmental pressures and emissions that are considered to be relevant (Figure 1). As the origin of the AoP concept (albeit it is often called differently) is older than LCA, it was used to guide the development of LCA methodology from the very beginning. One of the earliest

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FIGURE 1 Impact pathway leading from the technosphere to an area of protection.

conceptual documents on life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) (Fava, 1993) lists the AoPs (then called “categories of impacts”) of ecological health, human health, and resource depletion. The general themes stood the test of time, being also implicitly defined in the ISO (International Organization for Standardization) standard (Udo de Haes & Lindeijer, 2002).

Still, specific interpretations of what those themes entail vary. While the human health AoP appears to be accepted across the board, the views on the resources AoP have differed. How this AoP is variously interpreted is indicated by the different names used: “natural resources” (Dewulf et al., 2015; Udo de Haes et al., 1999), “resource base” (Goedkoop et al., 1998), “resources” (Hofstetter et al., 1999); or they were sometimes entirely omitted (Beltrani, 1997). The ecosystem health AoP, as outlined by Fava et al. (1993), consisted of the dimensions of structure, function, and biodiversity; but mostly it is understood as diversity of organisms and potential change in species richness (Verones et al., 2020). A separate AoP for “ecosystem services” was recently proposed to be added to represent the instrumental values of natural systems (Verones, Bare et al., 2017) or the dimension of ecosystem functioning (Hardaker et al., 2022). The recurring debates (Beltrani, 1997; Klöpffer, 2002) and attempts at reconsideration of the included AoPs (Dewulf et al., 2015; Verones, Bare et al., 2017) show there does not yet seem to be a definitive consensus on the AoPs. Ultimately, the selection and definition of AoPs is a value-based choice, thus it might be “possible to choose different categorizations of AoPs and related approaches to impact assessment that are equally acceptable for use in LCA” (Arnold Tukker in Klöpffer, 2002, p. 42).

Since the AoP selection is a value-based process and not a “natural fact,” it is clear that the underlying values can change in time. Similarly, the knowledge base grounding this decision evolves. One of the significant evolutions in environmental science, which has happened since the time the current AoPs were established, is the rise to prominence of Earth system science as a discipline (Steffen et al., 2020). With the great acceleration of human activity in the past century (Steffen, Broadgate et al., 2015), human environmental impacts are now truly global, although the responsibility for the impacts differs between different people and peoples. In this geological epoch called the Anthropocene (Malhi, 2017; Steffen et al., 2011; Waters et al., 2016), humans affect the very functioning of the Earth system and its regulatory processes. The Earth system is described as a complex-adaptive system, with nonlinear behavior, tipping points, and critical transitions (Reid et al., 2010; Steffen et al., 2020).

It is now increasingly clear that protecting local ecosystems and their services is not sufficient. The Earth system functioning itself needs to be preserved as well to allow a sustainable human civilization (Steffen et al., 2018). The general acceptance of this notion is demonstrated by the popularity of the concept of planetary boundaries (PB) (Richardson et al., 2023; Rockström et al., 2009; Steffen, Richardson et al., 2015) or the Earth system boundaries (Gupta et al., 2024; Rockström et al., 2023) and their vast application in environmental science and policy (Gupta et al., 2024; Rockström et al., 2024; Willett et al., 2019). The PBs have already penetrated the field of LCA with multiple studies comparing established impact categories with relevant PBs (Ryberg et al., 2018; Sala et al., 2020), or applying the PBs as normalization (Bjørn & Hauschild, 2015; De Laurentiis et al., 2023) or weighting factors (Tuomisto et al., 2012; Vargas-Gonzalez et al., 2019). Furthermore, the concept of planetary boundaries has inspired development of the Absolute Environmental Sustainability Assessment (AESAs) approach (Bjørn, Chandrakumar et al., 2020, 2019; Kosnik et al., 2022). Nevertheless, while all these approaches provide significant methodological innovation, it can be argued that the coupling with the PBs is often only superficial, not stressing the main characteristic and contribution of the PB concept which is the focus on Earth system functioning.

This article proposes the (Holocene-like) Earth system stability and functioning as an additional area of protection for the LCA framework. First, the general basis for defining an area of protection, as it is outlined in the available literature, is analyzed. Next, it is discussed whether, and how the Earth system functioning satisfies these principles and criteria. Furthermore, the potential impact pathways for the proposed AoP are outlined, and it is examined how they would differ from those targeting the current AoPs. Some available relevant methodologies focusing on the Earth system are discussed with particular focus on the AESA. Finally, the issues of space and time, as well as the issue of complexity are shortly discussed.

2 | EARTH SYSTEM AOP

2.1 | Basis for AoP definition

The broadest and simplest way to define the AoPs is as “the values that are considered important to society” (Verones, Bare et al., 2017, p. 959). However, such a definition is rather superficial and requires deeper reasoning. Beltrani (1997) states that “safeguard subjects are nothing else than elements of the natural environment which are considered to be intrinsically worth being protected” (p. 45). While this is probably the most common understanding, this means also that “the choice of safeguard subjects and their valuation needs to be made out of an environmental ethical argumentation” (Beltrani,

	HUMANS AND HUMAN-MADE SYSTEMS	NATURAL SYSTEMS	EARTH SYSTEM
INTRINSIC VALUES	Human health	Ecosystem quality	<i>Earth system functioning and stability</i>
FUNCTIONAL VALUES	<i>Socio-economic assets</i>	Natural resources, Ecosystem services	
CULTURAL VALUES	<i>Cultural heritage</i>	<i>Natural heritage</i>	

FIGURE 2 The overview of the areas of protection (AoPs) and the values the AoPs are based on. The AoPs which are yet to be operationalized are presented in italics. The proposed single Earth system AoP is based on, and transcending, all values. Figure based on Udo de Haes and Lindeijer (2002) and Verones, Bare et al. (2017).

1997, p. 45). Admittedly, this is problematic in that there are many value systems which could be applied, from anthropocentrism to ecocentrism and everything in between (Des Jardins, 2012; Minter, 2009; Rolston, 2020), and it would be incredibly hard, if not impossible, to get a general agreement on what is the ultimate value (Minter, 2009).

Schaubroeck and Rugani (2017) delved into value-based argumentation, albeit in the context of life cycle sustainability assessment, and concluded that sustainability is inherently anthropocentric and thus the only ultimate AoP should be human well-being. Notwithstanding that some might find this argumentation invalid and their conclusion unacceptable, Schaubroeck and Rugani (2017) do not argue the established AoPs should be abandoned, they delegated them to a status of “intermediate AoPs” which can be applied for practical reasons. However, contrary to such arguments, non-anthropocentric values are currently well embedded in the language of global legislation and policy. For example, the “Future We Want” (United Nations General Assembly, 2012)—the outcome document of the Conference on Sustainable Development in Rio—explicitly aims to “reaffirm the intrinsic value of biological diversity.” Indeed, the AoP of ecosystem quality in LCA is usually grounded on their intrinsic values (Udo de Haes & Lindeijer, 2002; Verones, Bare et al., 2017).

Nevertheless, it is not only intrinsic value that determines what is included among the AoPs. Udo de Haes and Lindeijer (2002) divide the world between human and natural spheres (Figure 2), and they apply criteria of intrinsic and functional values to derive multiple AoPs. Worth mentioning is their proposal of an AoP for life support functions of natural ecosystems, which sparked a lively debate (Klöpffer, 2002) but remained unheeded. Verones, Bare et al. (2017) later applied the same humans–nature divide too, considering the intrinsic, instrumental, and including also cultural values. This results in six potential AoPs, three corresponding to the currently established AoPs and three waiting for development (Figure 2). This shows that there are multiple principles to how AoPs can be defined; what is included among the AoPs is not a predetermined reality, rather a value-based choice which should represent relevant preferences.

2.2 | Defining the Earth system AoP

Following Earth system science, the Earth system can be considered a singular entity, a complex-adaptive system with its emergent properties and behavior. As a safeguard subject, it could be defined as the Holocene-like functioning and stability of the Earth system. The other AoPs can be seen as interacting with this larger system, affecting its functioning while being affected by it and dependent on it. The popularity of the planetary boundaries framework suggests there is a wide social (scientific) acceptance of the need to protect the stability of Earth system functioning. This, in turn, suggests the Earth system to be a relevant area of protection. Still, the argumentation for considering it in LCIA does not stand only on this apparent social acceptance. Whichever of the criteria for AoP selection are applied, it can be argued that Earth system as such fulfills them.

The “intrinsic value” argument is the strongest, but also the most contentious, depending on individual worldviews. Earth system is seen as a singular living entity in many indigenous worldviews (Kimmerer, 2013; Vetlesen, 2019), and, although not mainstream, there are western-based worldviews seeing the Earth as an entity too; consider, for example, the Gaia hypothesis (Lovelock, 2000, [1979]). Nevertheless, while the wide acceptance of the “natural ecosystems” as an intrinsic AoP shows that non-anthropocentric worldviews are well established, anthropocentrism still remains the norm, and it remains prominent in the LCA community as well (Schaubroeck & Rugani, 2017). The argument for Earth system AoP based on intrinsic values obviously would not be convincing to people with anthropocentric worldviews; and it might not be accepted by people with narrower non-anthropocentric views, such as sentientists or biocentrists neither (nor many other people with various worldviews).

When considering functional (instrumental) values as a basis for AoP selection, the Earth system is right on spot. Holocene-like conditions of the Earth system have been identified as a necessity for perseverance of a complex human civilization (Steffen et al., 2018), and thus it is a necessary safeguard subject for human well-being. Similarly, if the current state of the biosphere (ecosystems, species, landscapes, or individual organisms) is seen as inherently valuable, stable Earth system functioning is a clear necessity. While such argumentation may suggest that Earth system is but a midpoint to those AoPs, it can also be viewed from the other side: ecosystems (biosphere) and humans are an inseparable part, a sub-system of the

FIGURE 3 The binary position of the Earth system toward the established areas of protection (AoPs) and the intertwined, circular relationship of all the AoPs. The functioning of the Earth system influences the established AoPs of human health, ecosystem quality, and natural resources. On the other hand, human activity, ecosystem functioning, and resource flows have an effect on the state of the Earth system. Hence, Earth system can be considered both midpoint and endpoint in relation to current AoPs and would be better evaluated separately.

Earth system, affecting its functioning (Figure 3). For example, the loss of integrity of the Amazon forest would have wide consequences for Earth system stability (Flores et al., 2024). Similarly, since humans are one of the drivers of Earth system functioning in the Anthropocene (Malhi, 2017), a change in human activity driven by human health impacts or resource depletion can have an effect on the Earth system. From this perspective, it is human and ecosystem activity that is the midpoint to the Earth system AoP. This shows that the Earth system holds a binary position regarding other AoPs (Figure 3). There is not a linear, causal relationship between the AoPs, but they are all interacting and interconnected, which warrants them to be considered separately.

Earth system functioning is also vital for cultural values, which were proposed as another basis for AoPs by Verones, Bare et al. (2017). For example, regular climatic events and seasonality underline many cultural practices and have often been at the very basis of how people construct time and other basic elements of human conscience. Nevertheless, the role of Earth system as a cultural value is rather indirect. Cultural values are commonly quite contentious and often overlooked; hence the argument for inclusion as AoP on this basis is weaker. Still, the fact that Earth system AoP can be argued for on the basis of multiple valuation criteria affirms that it is a cross-cutting area which cannot be seen only as a midpoint to other AoPs. Human health AoP aims to protect humans as individuals, ecosystem health AoP aims to protect ecosystems (species) as individual elements disconnected. The Earth system AoP would add in the picture the systemic interconnections at the scale of broader systems. All the AoPs then have a dual role: they can be seen as ends in themselves as well as elements in and conditions for functioning of the other AoPs.

2.3 | Defining Earth system impact pathways

When Udo de Haes and Lindeijer (2002) proposed life support functions as a separate AoP, some argued that those subjects are already considered as midpoints to other AoPs (Klöpffer, 2002). Although the research over the past several decades of Earth system science provides much stronger grounding for a unique Earth system perspective, some might still claim that all the Earth system issues are already well covered by LCA. Indeed, when comparing the planetary boundaries with established impact categories, there appears to be a strong overlap (Fang et al., 2015; Sala et al., 2020). However, on a closer inspection this is an illusion. Parts of the impact pathways might well be shared among the Earth system AoP and the established AoPs. Greenhouse gas emissions aggregated as global warming potential seems like a natural midpoint for climate change even from the Earth system perspective. Similarly, anthropogenic nutrient flows are the cause of eutrophication impacts on ecosystems as well as a driver of a change in biogeochemical flows affecting Earth system functioning. However, some elements affect the traditional AoPs in such an indirect and complex way that they are entirely incompatible.

Indeed, the way the impact categories are modeled, and even which stressors are included, would differ for most issues, assuming the AoPs determine the structure of the modeled impact pathways. For example, the issue of land system change in the PBs is framed in the context of regulation of energy flows between land and the atmosphere. A corresponding LCIA indicator would focus on this effect (Bjørn, Sim et al., 2019) rather than on the impact on soil properties which is the current approach (De Laurentiis et al., 2019). The role of atmospheric aerosols in the Earth

FIGURE 4 The impact pathway leading from the pressure of water consumption, through streamflow disruption, toward four different areas of protection.

system relates to the change in atmospheric circulation (Richardson et al., 2023) or the changes in the dust cycle (Shao et al., 2011), which is an entirely different mechanism of impact to human inhalation currently captured in LCA (Fantke et al., 2016).

There are many elements in the Earth system worth protecting, and an effort to include them all could be overwhelming. The planetary boundaries (Richardson et al., 2023) or the Earth system boundaries (Rockström et al., 2023) can provide a preliminary guidance on the most important impact pathways and mechanisms which should be considered. There are also many other studies conceptualizing and analyzing individual Earth system issues in the planetary boundary language. Overall, the issues and impact pathways relevant to the Earth system AoP would well correspond to those of planetary boundaries, that is, “the biophysical and biochemical systems and processes known to regulate the state of the planet within ranges that are historically known and scientifically likely to maintain Earth system stability and life-support systems” (Richardson et al., 2023, p. 1). However, we stress that the goal of our proposal is not about application of the PBs as such. We see the PB framework as one manifestation of the ultimate goal of protecting Earth system functioning. PBs are designed on a global level with global models used to monitor the state of the system, and those are not directly applicable in LCA. The adoption of Earth system AoP in LCA would serve the same goal but on a different level, on the level of evaluating impacts on the Earth system attributable to the analyzed product, service, or a larger system.

Still, the PB or ESB frameworks propose control variables which could be classified as midpoint or endpoint, and the provided Earth system models could be utilized for impact category modeling. For example, the PB control variable for the functional element of the biospheric integrity measuring human appropriated net primary production corresponds more to the midpoint level while species extinction rate is positioned more toward the endpoint. Nevertheless, all those control variables would need to be translated to the level of impact rather than state (CO₂ emission rather than atmospheric concentration, change in radiative forcing rather than the total) to be applicable in LCA. Furthermore, many of the PB or ESB control variables are proposed only as preliminary proxy indicators. The potential LCIA indicators should push further to describe the impact pathways leading to a change in Earth system functioning as accurately as possible. At the AoP level, the individual impact categories could be aggregated, for example, on the basis of the distance from Holocene-like state, in a (hypothetical) unit of “potential Earth system disruption.” Yet for most elements of the Earth system, a change constituting an overshoot of a safe level could be clearly ascertained only at a larger level of aggregated impacts, not at the level of marginal change calculated in LCA. The best way of AoP-level aggregation of Earth system impacts would require a further debate and research before an adequate conclusion is reached.

2.4 | The cases of water and novel entities in the Earth system

Freshwater use makes a fitting example of how the Earth system AoP could affect the modeled impact pathway. Freshwater is relevant for all the proposed AoPs, but in a different way (Figure 4). On the endpoint level, the human health AoP focuses on the way water availability and quality impacts human health (expressed in DALY; Bulle et al., 2019; Debarre et al., 2022, 2024); ecosystem AoP focuses on the ecosystem damage (species loss expressed as potentially disappeared fraction [PDF]) (Pierrat, Barbarossa et al., 2023; Veronesi, Pfister et al., 2017) resulting directly from loss of water habitat or indirectly from drought, etc.; resources AoP could capture the impact of water scarcity on the economy and welfare provision. While all of these are valid and important concerns, the role of water in regulating Earth system functioning and its resilience (Gleeson, Wang-Erlandsson, Porkka et al., 2020) is clearly missing here. The Earth system AoP should focus on the water cycle change, “particularly change that is relevant to the hydroclimatic and hydroecological stability of the Earth system” (Porkka et al., 2024, p. 263). The overall impact on the water cycle can be captured through describing impacts on the six sub-elements (soil moisture, surface water, frozen water, groundwater, and two elements of

atmospheric water) outlined by Gleeson, Wang-Erlandsson, Zipper et al. (2020), forming a midpoint in the impact pathway. Some of those elements are already partly considered in existing models for other AoPs. For example, the effect on groundwater recharge is already a part of the Lanca model (Terranova et al., 2021), and global interactions in the water cycle are considered when water depletion is modeled (Pierrat, Dorber et al., 2023). However, those are interpreted in different contexts, soil quality and riverine fish diversity, respectively. Hence the effect on Earth system functioning is not revealed with those methods. Furthermore, some of the elements are as yet completely missing in LCA and the methods would need to be developed. One example could be a potential method describing the effect of land use change on evaporation–precipitation dynamics in the Earth system. Indicators for the different roles of water in Earth system functioning could potentially be aggregated into a single indicator in a similar way the soil quality index in the Lanca methodology is constructed (De Laurentiis et al., 2019).

Another apt example is in the issue of chemical pollution and novel entities. Currently, the LCIA methodologies aim to capture the direct toxic impacts on human health, and the ecotoxicological impacts on ecosystem quality. Methodologies targeting the Earth system AoP would need to follow different principles, not focusing on direct toxic impacts but rather on more systemic effects and on different aspects of chemical pollution. Such a process is, however, currently complicated by the fact that impacts of novel entities are largely a case of unknown unknowns (Persson et al., 2022), defined as causing so far unknown disruptions to Earth system functioning which manifest globally only when it is hard to reverse them. Therefore, the planetary boundary is currently defined only in the unit of emission of untested synthetics. While this could be a simple midpoint impact category in LCA, potentially useful for comparative assessments, a more complex impact pathway would need to be described to provide more insightful results. The impact pathway and the processes to be included could follow how the PB for novel entities is conceptualized (MacLeod et al., 2014; Persson et al., 2022, 2013). Furthermore, capturing the issue of plastic pollution with the Earth system AoP in mind would provide a different perspective to what is currently proposed (Woods et al., 2021). Rather than focusing on trying to quantify direct impacts on humans and ecosystems (Corella-Puertas et al., 2023; Lavoie et al., 2022), the methods could capture the effects of plastic pollution on the regulatory processes and cycles (Arp et al., 2021; Fabbri et al., 2021; Villarrubia-Gómez et al., 2018).

2.5 | Related approaches and methodologies

In recent years, multiple LCA methods have been proposed that specifically target the planetary boundaries or related issues. Many of them originate in the project of AESA. While the history of usage of biophysical limits or carrying capacities to assess “absolute sustainability” is much longer, the planetary boundaries framework played a significant role in its resurgence in the recent years (Li et al., 2021). Nevertheless, the scope of the AESA project goes beyond planetary boundaries and Earth system functioning. While there are proposed AESA characterization methods specifically addressing the water PB (Bjørn, Sim, Boulay et al., 2020; Li et al., 2020), land system PB (Bjørn, Sim et al., 2019), or the biogeochemical flows PB (Bjørn, Sim, King et al., 2020; Li et al., 2019), the AESA project is not limited to the PB or Earth system issues (Bjørn, Chandrakumar et al., 2020). For example, the AESA method for chemical pollution (Kosnik et al., 2022) captures ecotoxicological impacts in comparison to ecological limits, that is, the ecosystem quality AoP. Xue and Bakshi (2022) propose to base the limits on the “techno-ecological synergy” framework and ecosystem services provision rather than the planetary boundaries. That is to say that the proposal for Earth system AoP is in no way in conflict or competition with the AESA framework. The Earth system AoP would be relevant for both the traditional LCA approach as well as the AESA approach. In fact, adopting the Earth system AoP perspective could largely help to clarify the goal and approach for those AESA LCIA methods specifically addressing the PBs. Many of the specific methods could well be utilized in an Earth system AoP targeted methodology. Adding the Earth system AoP would allow a restructuring of the AESA framework, dividing AESA methods and limits based on human health, ecosystem health, resource provision, and the Earth system functioning as currently represented by the PBs.

2.6 | Spatial, temporal, and complexity issues

Attempts at quantifying impacts on the Earth system functioning AoP require dealing with the issues of space and time. Whether impacts and pressures are homogeneously distributed across the globe and across many years or concentrated in a single location and a point in time can determine whether it results in a marginal deterioration of conditions or an abrupt change in system functioning driven by a threshold crossing. For example, the same value of land use flows can mean a use of a small area of cropland distributed across a continent for decades, or occupation of an entire ecoregion in a single year. What distribution is preferable would depend on individual issues and systems. Nevertheless, this is not unique to this AoP, it affects the other AoPs as well. In fact, including the Earth system AoP in the framework could allow to divide the perspectives among AoPs. For example, concentration and persistence of pollutants affect the type and magnitude of toxic impacts. While the Earth system AoP should aim to include the pressures leading to systemic impacts and a change in Earth system functioning, the human health and ecosystem quality AoPs could focus on the impacts on individual humans and ecosystems, as they mostly do already. The issue of impact and pressure distribution is already acknowledged and sought to be ameliorated by increased regionalization (Mutel et al., 2019; Patouillard et al., 2018) and dynamic approaches (Levasseur et al., 2010). The same principles would apply to the Earth system AoP.

Yet another issue is the high complexity being one of the main properties of Earth system functioning and of its sub-systems. Being a complex-adaptive system, the Earth system is characterized by its high interconnectedness, nonlinear behavior, emergence, path dependencies, and threshold behavior (Steffen et al., 2005). This is at odds with the basic principles of LCA characterization which are based on linearity and additivity of impacts. While all social-ecological systems are complex systems (Biggs et al., 2015), and therefore this is a problem for all AoPs, it is arguably more significant for the Earth system which is targeted exactly for this complex behavior as the basis for life on Earth as we know it. Applying the common principles of characterization factor calculation, be it the average or marginal approach (Heijungs, 2021), would thus require even higher caution to ensure that the applied simplifications are justified. Furthermore, while the interactions among individual components are crucial for Earth system functioning (Lade et al., 2020), it does not yet seem viable to fully capture them in an LCIA framework. A *ceteris paribus* approach to impact modeling would probably need to be taken in the same way that individual stressors to human health or ecosystem quality are modeled separately in current LCA. However, prospective characterization factors considering scenarios of potential Anthropocene trajectories could partly help. Withal, it is paramount that the characterization factors are applied on the level they were designed (marginal change). LCA characterization factors, unless specifically designed for this purpose, should not be used to evaluate impacts of a magnitude triggering threshold and tipping points that change the behavior of the system to the degree that the conditions of the model are no longer valid.

The goal of LCA is not to quantify absolute, real impacts but to evaluate potential impacts, not to predict absolute impacts on endpoints but to provide relative expressions (Guinée et al., 2022; ISO: 14044, 2006). In that matter, the goal of the proposed LCIA methods targeting the Earth system AoP is not to quantify precisely the changes in Earth system functioning as they occur (i.e., the goal of Earth system science and Earth system modeling) but to keep track of potential impacts stemming from product systems, organization activity, or to guide wider transformative strategies (Hellweg et al., 2023). The discussions in this section clearly show that what is proposed here is not a fundamentally different methodology, no revolution is proposed. Each new impact category and characterization model would certainly come with its own problems and would require innovative solutions. Some new impact categories would require new elementary flows and new models while many could utilize those already available. Although a lot of the necessary data and knowledge are currently missing, as shown in the example of novel entities, establishing the Earth system AoP could provide an impetus for this research. Nevertheless, the established rules and principles of LCIA should be adhered to in order to maintain the nature of LCA.

Earth system impacts are currently partly considered or mixed in with impact categories capturing the standard AoPs, and hence there is a danger that the Earth system AoP indicators could be seen as redundant. Adding another AoP may appear as only adding further complication to interpreting LCA results, when the goal of many is to standardize and reduce the number of indicators (Brandão et al., 2024). On the other hand, it can be seen as providing a structure and a clear goal to a process that is already happening. As described above, LCA is already widely applied and interpreted in the context of planetary boundaries, notably with the AESA approach. Furthermore, many Earth system issues remain unassessed, and their inclusion would provide a different perspective to LCA results and potentially valuable guidance for policymaking. As the relevance of Earth system impacts for practitioners and policymakers is more and more evident (Gupta et al., 2024), it is up for a debate whether the added information value is worth the risk of higher complexity of LCA results.

3 | CONCLUSION

The proposed Earth system functioning AoP aims to extend the horizon of LCA studies to capture the impacts on the Earth system which are currently missing. It was shown that Earth system AoP can be argued for considering various criteria, based on intrinsic value, functional value, as well as cultural value. Earth system has a binary relationship to the currently established AoPs and therefore cannot be considered as just a midpoint to the current AoP but an issue of its own. Including the Earth system as an AoP would allow LCA analyzes to consider different impact pathways and thus different dimensions of the current environmental issues. This is but a first attempt at a broad conceptualization of an Earth system AoP which would require further scientific debate and methodological development to be fully operational. Full operationalization of the Earth system AoP would require developing a consensual definition of this AoP. Next steps would entail outlining relevant impact pathways, defining relevant impact categories, and, finally, developing characterization models for those categories. Furthermore, whether a common endpoint unit for this AoP, similar to DALY and PDF, can be found for this AoP, and which it would be, remains an open question. Those discussions can be grounded in and inspired by the knowledge from Earth system science as well as available research in the LCA field, but a lot of further research would be required. The current planetary crises, the state of transgression of multiple planetary boundaries (Richardson et al., 2023), and the overall findings of Earth system science suggest that this perspective expansion is long overdue.

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Data sharing is not applicable as no new data were generated.

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